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Personality Traits as Correlates of Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between personality traits and marital stability among married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. A correlational survey design was adopted, guided by five research questions. Five hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The population comprised 47,444 married parishioners across 11 deaneries, from which a sample of 385 respondents was selected using Cochran's formula and a multi-stage sampling procedure. Data were collected using adapted versions of Fetzer's Big Five Inventory (FBFI) and TREK's Marital Stability Questionnaire (MSQ). The instruments yielded reliability coefficients of 0.70 and 0.80 respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used for data analysis. The findings revealed that all five Big Five personality traits; openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism had significant relationships with marital stability among the respondents. The study concluded that spouses' personality dispositions play a significant role in sustaining stable marriages within the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi. Based on the findings, the study recommended targeted marital counselling interventions focusing on personality development, emotional regulation, effective communication, and responsibility to enhance marital stability.

Keywords: Personality Traits, Big Five Personality Traits; Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, Neuroticism and Marital Stability.

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is a sacred institution that plays a crucial role in shaping the emotional, social and spiritual well-being of individuals and society at large. As an institution of divine origin, God intended marriage to be a lifelong covenant and should be entered into mainly through a free and irrevocable consent of the man and the woman. In the Catholic Church, marriage is considered a sacred and lifelong covenant between couples, emphasizing values such as love, commitment, fidelity and mutual support. Thus, God's original intention for marriage was for stability and permanence. This divine intention of stability and permanence in marriage has been adequately explained in the teachings of Jesus Christ about marriage and divorce. When some Pharisees confronted Jesus Christ about the possibility of divorce, he said to them that from creation God made them male and female and "for this reason a man shall leave his father and mother and

be joined to his wife, and the two shall become one flesh. So, they are no longer two but one flesh. Therefore, what God has joined together, let no one separate” (Mark 10:6-9 NJB).

Marital stability is the divine plan for every marriage. Muchope (2022), asserts that marital stability is the total understanding, satisfaction, fidelity, commitment and cohesion couples feel in a marriage in spite of conflicts. The author maintained that it is the healthiness, maturity and permanence a marriage enjoys in spite of conflicts, misunderstandings, misconceptions or misinterpretations of one’s spouse’s thoughts and intentions. This implies that every Christian marriage should experience stability since the divine plan is for couples to remain legally married without divorce and physical or legal separation.

Marital stability is anchored on different factors. These may include love, commitment, trust, time, communication, tolerance, patience, openness, honesty, respect, sharing, consideration, generosity, sacrifice, willingness and ability to compromise ones standards, ideologies and principles to accommodate one’s spouse’s needs (American Psychology Association, 2023). Aghadinazu (2021), explains further that promoting stability in marriage requires spending time with one’s spouse, learning to negotiate conflict, showing respect for each other at all times, learning more about each other as couple and exploring intimacy and common interest through constant and healthy communication. The researcher has observed that marital stability is fast switching roles with marital instability in many Christian marriages simply because couples lack the ability to resolve their conflicts themselves peacefully without involving a third party.

The researcher has observed that, despite the Catholic Church’s strong emphasis on the permanence of marriage, there has been a noticeable increase in couples within the Diocese of Makurdi seeking pastoral counselling for unresolved marital issues. Some couples have even turned to informal separations or pursued annulments. This pattern indicates that personal and psychological factors may be influencing marital stability, yet these issues have not been fully addressed. The prevalence of marital conflicts and crises among Christian couples in the area has become a significant concern. In many parishes, priests dedicate substantial time to managing marital disputes, while religious leaders, psychologists, and counsellors frequently handle numerous cases each year to prevent separation or divorce. Observations suggest that the rate of marital breakdown in the Diocese of Makurdi has risen over the past five years. According to the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi Marriage Tribunal (2024), nearly six hundred petitions for separation or divorce were submitted during this period, with over two hundred marriages annulled and several others still under review. It is important to state that marital instability is not peculiar to the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria; it is an increasingly significant social issue around the world. Once considered a personal or family matter, it is now acknowledged as a public concern with far-reaching social, emotional, economic and educational consequences. While marital instability is a global phenomenon, it manifests differently across countries and cultures due to variations in social norms, legal frameworks, and economic conditions.

Globally, the institution of marriage has undergone profound transformation. Traditional notions of lifelong marriage are being replaced by more flexible and individualistic concepts. Global divorce rates have risen, particularly in developed nations. According to the World Population Review (2024), countries such as the United States, Russia, and South Korea have among the highest divorce rates in the world. The United States, for instance, reports approximately 2.7 divorces per 1,000 population, while the Maldives continues to experience the highest global rate at 5.52 per 1,000 (Cary, 2023). Studies (Karney & Bradbury, 2020) suggest that factors such as modernization and urbanization, gender equality, changing social attitudes, and the advent of technology and social media may be responsible for this trend.

In Nigeria, marriage is deeply embedded in cultural and religious traditions. While marriage is still highly valued, recent trends indicate an increase in both formal divorces and informal separations, especially in urban areas. According to data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2022), divorce rates in Nigeria have risen modestly, with urban centers like Lagos and Abuja showing the highest incidence. Studies (Lyu & Zhang, 2019), suggest that high unemployment, inflation, poverty and conflicting gender roles have contributed to stress and dissatisfaction within marriages. Despite the Church’s teachings on

the indissolubility of marriage, many couples still face challenges that threaten marital stability thereby leading to instability in marriages. The researcher has observed that marital instability, characterized by frequent conflicts, dissatisfaction, separation or divorce, has become a growing concern in various societies, including the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. And this issue of marital instability has been attributed to various issues including the personality of both or either parties involved in marriage, socio-demographic factors, biological factors, among others.

Personality traits in particular have been a recurring decimal in studies on marriage and marital stability. Yalçın and Karahan (2020) affirmed that one of the significant factors influencing marital stability is personality traits. Personality traits are enduring patterns of thoughts, emotions, motivations, and behaviours that distinguish individuals from one another. They are relatively stable over time and consistent across various situations, yet they can evolve through personal growth and life experiences. According to Soto and Jackson (2020), personality traits represent the fundamental dimensions of human psychological differences, shaping how individuals perceive, interpret, and respond to the world around them. These traits influence not only behaviour but also long-term outcomes such as mental health, career success, and interpersonal relationships. Personality traits serve as building blocks of personality. They are distinct from fleeting moods or situational responses; rather, they form core tendencies that influence how a person acts across various settings. Several models have been developed to conceptualize and measure personality traits. Each model offers a unique perspective on the structure and function of personality. The most prominent among these are the Big Five Personality Traits Model, Eysenck's Three-Factor Model, Cattell's 16 Personality Factor Model and the HEXACO model. However, for the purpose of this study we shall focus on the Big Five personality Model.

The Big Five Personality traits model was developed by Robert R. McCrae and Paul Costa in 1987. It is a model that is represented by the acronym OCEAN. This can be expressed as Openness (O), Conscientiousness (C), Extraversion (E), Agreeableness (A) and Neuroticism (N). To further contextualize this trait within the Big Five framework, openness has been discussed by contemporary scholars as a key dimension associated with curiosity, creativity, and receptiveness to new experiences and ideas.

Openness has been defined by Soto (2018) as a personality trait that reflects individual differences in imagination, aesthetic sensitivity, intellectual curiosity, and a preference for novelty and variety of experiences. The author maintained that, individuals high in openness tend to be curious, creative, and receptive to new ideas, whereas those low in openness prefer familiarity, routine, and conventional ways of thinking. Crystal (2024) concisely added that openness is a trait that describes one's open-mindedness to learn new things. One's character or behaviour can be open or closed to experiences. Studies (McCrae & Costa, 2017) have shown that couples who are high in openness tend to have a broad range of interests and are curious about the world and other people, eager to learn new things, and inclined to enjoy novel experiences. One's spouse can either be open or closed; therefore, understanding the personality of the person one lives with, particularly in terms of openness, may be crucial to a healthy and stable relationship. The openness-to-experience trait of an individual forms the basis of the inquisitive scale and the learning approach scale, which assess creativity, curiosity, abstract thinking, imagination, and the ability to learn new things (Kendra, 2023; Crystal, 2024). These scales evaluate an individual's imaginative capacity and problem-solving skills, implying that spouses who are open tend to be creative, flexible, curious, and unconventional in marriage (McCrae & Costa, 2017). Such traits provide fertile ground for love, forgiveness, trust, and fidelity within marital relationships. Openness may be high or low among individuals; couples high in openness are often more adaptable and use their creativity to address marital challenges, whereas those low in openness tend to resist change, dislike new ideas, and show limited imagination, which may affect marital stability positively or negatively (Soto, 2018).

Building on openness as a trait concerned with curiosity and receptiveness to new experiences, conscientiousness represents a complementary dimension of personality that emphasizes regulation, responsibility, and goal-directed behavior. Soto (2018) defines conscientiousness as a personality trait that reflects individual differences in self-discipline, organization, persistence, and the tendency to plan and

regulate behavior in the service of long-term goals. Jayson (2024), further explains that couples with high conscientious behaviour spend time preparing for things and that helps them to finish important marital tasks or other tasks right on time and accurately too. This is because they pay attention to details and enjoy having a set schedule. Conversely, low conscientious couples are less structured and organized. They may procrastinate to get things done and sometimes missing deadlines completely (Jayson, 2024). This may not be too good in early marriage relationship. Other studies have shown that, low conscientious couples are likely to dislike structured and well planned schedules. They make mess of things and are fond of not taking care of things. They also fail to return things or put them back where they belong. They are also known to procrastinate and fail to complete necessary or assigned tasks (Hill, Turiano, Hurd, Mroezek & Roberts, 2013). Stability of a marriage or relationship may be dependent on understanding one's spouse's personality trait based on conscientiousness. This could help one to be fully ready for certain behaviour and how to handle them in marriage for healthy and stable relationship. Beyond conscientiousness, which emphasizes structure, discipline, and goal-directed behavior within marriage, extraversion introduces an interpersonal dimension of personality that focuses on sociability, emotional expressiveness, and the manner in which spouses engage with one another and their social environment.

Extraversion personality trait is the third trait in the order of arrangement and it describes an individual's features of excitability, sociability, talkativeness, assertiveness and high amounts of emotional expressiveness (Mesurado, Mateo, Marshall & Richard, 2014). Couples who are excited about their marriage are sociable and find every opportunity to discuss their marriage strengths and weaknesses with their spouses or others freely. This trait may be what most Christian couples need to explore the complexity and challenges that come with marriage. Couples with high extraversion are likely to be outgoing and tend to gain energy for social situations. They love to be around others and this helps them to feel energized and excited all the time. This could spice up one's relationship in marriage and help to build a stable and permanent home. However, couples with low extraversion are more likely to be reserved with less energy to expend in social settings and events (Meyer, 2024). Christian couples need to understand their spouses and accept them for who they are. This could be crucial to building a stable and healthy relationship with peace, trust, love and forgiveness would thrive. Building on extraversion, agreeableness adds another important dimension by highlighting how empathy, cooperation, and compassion shape interactions between spouses and contribute to marital harmony.

Agreeableness is the fourth personality trait among the big five model that talks about attributes such as trust, altruism, kindness, affection, cooperation and understanding. Wilmot (2024), notes that agreeableness deals with an individual's interest, care, empathy, concern and ability to enjoy helping and contributing to the happiness of other people and assisting others who are in need of help. Couples who possess this trait could meet the emotional, social and moral needs of the partners. Couples with high agreeableness are likely to have great interest in others and care more about the needs of others even the spouse. However, couples with low agreeableness trait may have little interest in others, and care less about how other people and even their spouse feel. They have little interest in their spouse's problem. They may insult and belittle others easily and are likely to be very manipulative to get what they want (Tip & Ingemar, 2021; Gordon, 2023). Couples who pay attention to their partners' personality traits and understand them could find way on how to live with the strengths and weaknesses of such trait as agreeableness and how best to improve on them. While agreeableness promotes cooperation, empathy, and harmony in marital relationships, neuroticism represents a contrasting trait that reflects emotional instability and vulnerability to negative emotions, which can challenge relationship satisfaction and stability.

Neuroticism is the last and fifth personality trait that is characterized by behaviours such as sadness, moodiness, and emotional instability. Widiger and Oltmanns (2017), assert that neuroticism is a personality trait that describes the emotional state of an individual such as emotional resilient or mood swings. The success of every marriage and relationship may be dependent on the understanding of whether or not an individual or spouse has the neurotic trait. This may enable couples to make-up or

complement their spouse's weaknesses. Couples with high neuroticism trait are likely to experience a lot of stress, worries about different things and get upset easily. However, couples with low neuroticism trait could be emotionally stable and have the ability to deal well with stress and they rarely feel sad or depressed and worry less (Widiger & Oltmanns, 2017; Arlin, 2023). Low neuroticism trait is what every Christian couple may need to enjoy their marriage and stay healthy in their relationship as husband and wife.

Based on the roles of the big five personality traits in the understanding of an individual, and how he behaves, the need to investigate its relationship in marriage is eminent. In the context of the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, traditional values and religious doctrines emphasize the sanctity of marriage, marital permanence, and the resolution of marital conflicts through faith-based counselling and community support. Therefore, there is a need to examine how personality traits, specifically the Big Five personality traits, interact with Christian marital values to either enhance or undermine marital stability. This is because, while existing research has explored factors such as communication styles, financial stability and cultural differences on marital outcomes, limited studies have specifically examined the role of personality traits in determining marital stability among Catholic couples in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

Given the increasing cases of marital discord, separations and even annulments in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi as observed by the researcher, understanding the relationship between personality traits and marital stability may be critical in developing strategies for premarital counselling, marriage enrichment programmes and pastoral interventions. This study, therefore, focuses on investigating the relationship between personality traits, specifically the big five personality traits, (openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism) and marital stability among Christian couples in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

Marriage, as a sacred institution in the Catholic Church, is expected to be stable, fulfilling, and lifelong. Yet, despite the religious teachings, premarital counselling, and pastoral guidance offered by the Church, many Christian marriages in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi continue to experience instability, manifested in domestic violence, conflicts, separations, and even divorce. Reports of marital dissatisfaction and recurring disputes among married parishioners have raised concerns about the factors contributing to these challenges. While issues such as financial stress, cultural expectations, infidelity, and family interference have been identified as potential causes of marital instability, the influence of individual personality traits on marital outcomes has received comparatively less attention, particularly within the religious and cultural context of the Diocese.

Observations within the Diocese reveal that, despite the Church's emphasis on the permanence of marriage, a growing number of couples seek pastoral counselling for unresolved marital issues, with some resorting to informal separations or annulments. This trend points to the possible role of underlying personal and psychological factors in marital instability that have not been adequately addressed. The high incidence of marital conflict in the Diocese is evident in the workload of priests, religious leaders, psychologists, and counsellors, who dedicate substantial time each year to resolving marital disputes and preventing separations or divorce. Data from the Marriage Tribunal of the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi (2024) indicates that nearly six hundred petitions for separation or divorce were filed in the past five years, with over two hundred marriages annulled and several others still under review. These troubling observations underscore the need to explore how the individual personality traits of Christian couples may contribute to marital stability or instability. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate personality traits as correlates of marital stability among Christian couples in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between openness and marital stability of married parishioners?
2. What is the relationship between conscientiousness and marital stability of married parishioners?
3. What is the relationship between extraversion and marital stability of married parishioners?

4. What is the relationship between agreeableness and marital stability of married parishioners?
5. What is the relationship between neuroticism and marital stability of married parishioners?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Openness has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners.
2. Conscientiousness has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners.
3. Extraversion has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners.
4. Agreeableness has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners.
5. Neuroticism has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational survey design. The area of the study is Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. The population of this study comprised 47,444 married parishioners across the 11 Deaneries that make up the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. The sample size of this study consisted of 385 married parishioners, arrived at by using Cochran’s formula for selecting sample size. The study adopted multi-stage sampling procedure to select the sample. The researcher adapted two instruments for data collection. They included: Fetzer’s Big Five Inventory (FBFI) and TREK’s Marital Stability Questionnaire (MSQ). The FBFI, reliability analysis yielded total reliability coefficient for the FBFI was 0.70. The second instrument (MSQ) yielded a total reliability coefficient of 0.80. To analyze the data, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to answer the research questions. Similarly, PPMCC was also used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between openness and marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State?*

Table 1: Correlation Openness and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Openness	Marital Instability
Openness	Pearson Correlation	1	.531**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	.531**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385

Table 1 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for openness to experience and marital stability. Results indicate a moderate positive correlation $r = .531$, suggesting that higher levels of openness are associated with greater marital stability among married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Research Question 2: *How does conscientiousness correlate with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State?*

Table 2: Correlation Conscientiousness and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Conscientiousness	Marital Instability
Conscientiousness	Pearson Correlation	1	.508**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	.508**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385

Table 2 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for conscientiousness and marital stability. Results indicate a moderate positive correlation $r = .508$, suggesting that higher levels of conscientiousness are associated with greater marital stability among married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. This implies that individuals who are more conscientious are also more likely to experience stable marriages.

Research Question 3: *How does extraversion correlate with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State?*

Table 3: Correlation Extraversion and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Extraversion	Marital Instability
Extraversion	Pearson Correlation	1	.519**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	.519**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385

Table 3 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for extraversion and marital stability. Results indicate a moderate positive correlation was found between extraversion and marital stability, $r = .52$, among married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. This implies that individuals who are more extraverted tend to experience greater marital stability.

Research Question 4: *How does agreeableness correlate with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State?*

Table 4: Correlation Agreeableness and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Agreeableness	Marital Instability
Agreeableness	Pearson Correlation	1	.524**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	.524**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385

Table 4 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for agreeableness and marital stability. Results indicate a moderate positive correlation was found between agreeableness and marital stability, $r = .52$, among married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. This implies that individuals who are more agreeable tend to experience greater marital stability.

Research Question 5: *How does neuroticism correlate with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State?*

Table 5: Correlation Neuroticism and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Neuroticism	Marital Instability
Neuroticism	Pearson Correlation	1	-.423**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	-.423**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	385	385

Table 5 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for neuroticism and marital stability. Results indicate a weak negative correlation was found between neuroticism and marital stability, $r = -.42$, among married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. This implies that individuals who are more neurotic tend to experience lower levels of marital stability.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1

Openness has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Table 6: Relationship Between Openness and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Openness	Marital Instability
Openness	Pearson Correlation	1	.531**
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))		.000
	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	.531**	1
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))	.000	
	N	385	385

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 6 shows the Pearson product moment correlation results for openness to experience and marital stability. Results indicate a significant moderate positive correlation $r = .531, p < .05$, suggesting that higher levels of openness are associated with greater marital stability. Since the p-value, .000 is less than .05 the null hypothesis which stated that openness has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State is rejected. This implies that openness has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Hypothesis 2

Conscientiousness has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State

Table 7: Relationship Between Conscientiousness and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Conscientiousness	Marital Instability
Conscientiousness	Pearson Correlation	1	.508**
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))		.000
	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	.508**	1
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))	.000	
	N	385	385

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 7 shows the Pearson product moment correlation results for conscientiousness and marital stability. Results indicate a significant moderate positive correlation $r = .508, p < .05$, suggesting that higher levels of conscientiousness are associated with greater marital stability. This implies that individuals who are more conscientious are also more likely to experience stable marriages. Therefore, since the p-value, .000 is less than .05 the null hypothesis which stated that conscientiousness has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State is rejected. This implies that conscientiousness has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Hypothesis 3

Extraversion has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State

Table 8: Relationship Between Extraversion and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Extraversion	Marital Instability
Extraversion	Pearson Correlation	1	.519**
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))		.000

	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	.519**	1
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))	.000	
	N	385	385

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 8 shows the Pearson product moment correlation results for extraversion and marital stability. Results indicate a significant moderate positive correlation was found between extraversion and marital stability, $r = .52, p < .05$, indicating that individuals who are more extraverted tend to experience greater marital stability. Therefore, since the p-value, .000 is less than .05 the null hypothesis which stated that extraversion has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State is rejected. This implies that extraversion has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Hypothesis 4

Agreeableness has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State

Table 9: Relationship Between Agreeableness and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Agreeableness	Marital Instability
Agreeableness	Pearson Correlation	1	.524**
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))		.000
	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	.524**	1
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))	.000	
	N	385	385

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 9 shows the Pearson product moment correlation results for agreeableness and marital stability. Results indicate a significant moderate positive correlation was found between agreeableness and marital stability, $r = .52, p < .05$, indicating that individuals who are more agreeable tend to experience greater marital stability. Therefore, since the p-value, .000 is less than .05 the null hypothesis which stated that agreeableness has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State is rejected. This implies that agreeableness has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Hypothesis 5

Neuroticism has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State

Table 10: Relationship Between Neuroticism and Marital Stability among Married Parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

Variables		Neuroticism	Marital Instability
Neuroticism	Pearson Correlation	1	-.423**
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))		.000
	N	385	385
Marital Instability	Pearson Correlation	-.423**	1
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))	.000	
	N	385	385

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 10 shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation results for neuroticism and marital stability. Results indicate a significant weak negative correlation was found between neuroticism and marital stability, $r = -.42, p < .05$, indicating that individuals who are more neurotic tend to experience lower levels of marital stability. Therefore, since the p-value, .000 is less than .05 the null hypothesis which stated that neuroticism has no significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the

Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State is rejected. This implies that neuroticism has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding revealed that openness has a relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. In correspondence with the first research question, the first null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that openness has a relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. This finding implies that couples who are imaginative, curious, and willing to engage in new experiences are more likely to adapt positively to marital changes, communicate effectively, and handle conflicts constructively. This is consistent with the study by Johnson, Okafor, and Mensah (2024), which reported that openness positively predicted marital stability among Christian couples in Lagos, improving communication and adaptability. Similarly, Bello, Eze, and Mensim (2024) found that openness enhances emotional connection and conflict resolution in long-term Christian marriages. Couples who are imaginative, curious, and receptive to new experiences are more likely to adapt to changes in marriage, communicate effectively, and manage conflicts constructively. Openness appears to facilitate flexibility in handling marital challenges, which can strengthen emotional intimacy and cooperation between spouses. In practical terms, understanding a spouse's level of openness may help couples navigate differences and explore shared activities that enhance marital satisfaction and thereby stability.

The second finding showed that conscientiousness has a relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. Corresponding to the second research question, the second null hypothesis was rejected, suggesting that conscientiousness has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. Conscientious couples tend to be responsible, organized, and diligent in fulfilling marital roles, which promotes trust and long-term stability. Thompson and Clark (2024) similarly found that conscientious spouses demonstrated higher marital satisfaction due to their reliability and structured approach to household and relational responsibilities. Oladipo and Uzoma (2024) also reported that conscientiousness positively predicted problem-solving and emotional intimacy in marital relationships. These findings highlight that conscientiousness is crucial for maintaining consistent effort and commitment within marriages, thereby reducing the likelihood of marital conflict and instability. Couples who are organized, responsible, and dependable tend to maintain higher levels of commitment and consistency in their relationships. Conscientious spouses are likely to fulfill their marital roles, keep promises, and manage responsibilities efficiently, all of which contribute to a more stable and predictable marital environment. Recognizing the role of conscientiousness may help couples develop routines and strategies that reinforce trust and mutual support in marriage.

The third finding revealed that extraversion has a relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. In line with the third research question, the third null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that extraversion has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. Yakubu and Chikere (2024) reported a positive correlation between extraversion and marital stability among Christian couples in Enugu, showing that extraverted individuals enhance relational satisfaction and interpersonal dynamics. Similarly, Nazari, Sardaripoor, Kakavand, and Mansobifar (2020) observed that extraversion contributes to marital cohesion by promoting engagement and emotional expressiveness between spouses. These results suggest that extraversion may facilitate connection and relational energy, which supports marital continuity and stability. Extraverted individuals are sociable, expressive, and energetic, which can promote open communication and positive interactions within the marriage. Couples with higher levels of extraversion may engage more frequently in social and recreational activities together, enhancing relational closeness and satisfaction. This finding suggests that extraversion can be a source of relational vitality, helping couples maintain engagement and connection over time.

The fourth finding indicated that agreeableness has a relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. Corresponding to the fourth research question, the fourth null hypothesis was rejected, suggesting that agreeableness has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. Khosravi and Mehr (2024) found that agreeableness positively predicted marital satisfaction and emotional cohesion, reinforcing that kind and cooperative behaviors foster marital stability. Wright and Hanson (2024) also reported that agreeable partners contribute to reduced conflict and improved communication, which are critical factors in sustaining long-term marital relationships. The present finding implies that cultivating agreeableness in couples may enhance relational harmony and strengthen marital stability. Spouses who are empathetic, cooperative, and supportive are better able to resolve conflicts amicably and maintain harmonious relationships. Agreeableness facilitates compromise, understanding, and concern for the partner's well-being, which fosters trust and mutual respect. This implies that cultivating kindness, patience, and cooperation in couples may enhance marital harmony and reduce the likelihood of disputes.

Finally, the fifth finding revealed that neuroticism has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. In line with the fifth research question, the fifth null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that neuroticism has a significant relationship with marital stability of married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. Couples high in neuroticism are prone to conflicts, anxiety, and dissatisfaction, while emotionally stable partners demonstrate resilience and coping ability that support marital continuity. This aligns with Mehta and Iyer (2024), who found that neuroticism negatively influenced marital adjustment and intimacy, and Ariski and Nurhayati (2021), who reported that neuroticism undermines marital quality. These findings suggest that managing emotional instability and promoting emotional resilience in couples could be vital for sustaining a stable and fulfilling marriage. High levels of neuroticism, characterized by emotional instability, stress, and overthinking, can negatively impact marital stability by increasing conflicts and reducing satisfaction. Conversely, low neuroticism is associated with resilience, emotional regulation, and better coping mechanisms, which support relationship continuity. This finding highlights the importance of managing negative emotions and developing emotional stability as a means to maintain a healthy and lasting marriage.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that personality traits have significant relationship with marital stability among married parishioners in the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State. All five dimensions of the Big Five personality traits namely; openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism were found to have significant relationships with marital stability, indicating that the personal dispositions of spouses are important factors in sustaining stable and enduring marriages within the Catholic Diocese of Makurdi, Benue State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Marriage counsellors should encourage couples to develop openness by fostering flexibility, creativity, and willingness to embrace change within marriage..
2. Counsellors are advised to emphasize the importance of responsibility, planning, and commitment in marital relationships. Through counselling, couples may be guided to set clear marital goals, manage responsibilities effectively, and cultivate dependable behaviours. Strengthening conscientious behaviours in couples could improve consistency, trust, and long-term commitment in marriage.
3. Marriage counsellors should help couples leverage healthy social interaction and effective communication skills associated with extraversion. Counselling programmes could include communication-enhancement strategies that encourage emotional expressiveness, positive

interaction, and shared social engagement, while also helping less extraverted spouses feel understood and respected within the relationship.

4. Counsellors should focus on nurturing agreeableness by promoting empathy, kindness, cooperation, and conflict resolution skills among couples. Structured counselling interventions that teach patience, forgiveness, and compromise may help couples manage disagreements constructively and maintain harmony, thereby contributing to stable and supportive marriages.
5. Given the significant relationship between neuroticism and marital stability, counsellors should assist couples in identifying and managing emotional instability, stress, and negative emotional patterns.

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